

ANALYSES OF MECHANICAL REINFORCEMENT FOR CELLULOSE NANOFIBERS/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES USING X-RAY DIFFRACTION

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we focused on stress transfer in the composites composed of montmorillonite (MMT) and cellulose nanofibers. We employed mechanically fibrillated cellulose nanofibers (FCN) using microfluidizer and TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanofibers (TOCN), and also prepared two types of MMT with sodium and quaternary ammonium cations as interlayer ions. We used the cellulose nanofibers as matrixes and the MMTs as reinforcement fillers to prepare nanocomposites by simply mixing both aqueous dispersions. X-ray diffraction method was performed in order to investigate stress transfer systems in these nanocomposites. The TOCN-based nanocomposites showed higher Young's modulus as well as larger stress transfer coefficient than the FCN-based ones, which was attributed to strong interfacial interaction between TOCN and MMT.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is well known as the most abundant renewable polymer on the earth and plays a significant role in the structural support of plant cell walls because of its high mechanical properties [1]. Nowadays, cellulose is widely studied fundamentally to satisfy the demands for eco-friendly and biocompatible products in industrial applications. In addition, cellulose nanofibers (CNF) are receiving much attention because of their remarkable properties, such as high aspect ratio, high crystallinity, and high mechanical properties [2].

Several methods for preparing CNF have been reported, such as mechanical fibrillation by grinder [3], chemical fibrillation by TEMPO-mediated oxidation [4] and so on. These CNF with various fibrillation methods have different structures and properties. Therefore, it is important to investigate the dependence of their properties on their fibrillation processes for practical application.

Montmorillonite (MMT) is one of the typical clays, which has been conventionally used in the polymer/clay nanocomposites. MMT is a two-dimensional nano-plates, with only 1 nm thickness and high aspect ratio which ranging is 10-1000 [5]. MMT is known to be dispersed in water stably and homogeneously, because of its hydrophilic surface. In addition, CNF are also dispersed in water. Thus, it can be expected that they are compounded eco-friendly with simple mixing procedure.

In this study, we employed CNF as a matrix and MMT as a filler, then prepared CNF/MMT nanocomposites through mixing both aqueous dispersions. Two types of CNF were prepared by mechanical and chemical fibrillations for evaluation of interaction between CNF matrix and MMT fillers. The reinforcement effect of MMT were investigated by stress transfer using "X-ray diffraction method" [6]. We evaluated the stress on MMT in the nanocomposites under load, and the stress transfer system from CNF to MMT was discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Bast fibers of kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus*, Indonesia, 2011) were supplied from Toyota Boshoku Co. (Japan), used as CNF. MMT powder "Kunipia-G" was supplied from Kunimine Industries Co., Ltd.

(Japan). Toluene, ethanol (EtOH), Sodium chlorite (NaClO_2), sodium hypochlorite (NaClO), sodium bromide (NaBr), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), acetic acid and tetraethylammonium hydroxide were purchased from Nacalai Tesque, Inc. (Japan). TEMPO was purchased from Hydrus Chemical Inc. (Japan). All reagents were used without further purification.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Purification of cellulose from Kenaf

According to reported literature [7], cellulose was refined from bast fibers of kenaf by removing grease through Soxhlet extraction in EtOH/toluene, lignin with Wise methods, and hemicellulose using alkaline treatment. These refined fibers were never dried for the following processes of fibrillation.

Preparation of CNF by mechanical fibrillation

The refined kenaf fiber was subjected to a pre-treatment step, followed by fibrillation by a homogenization step with a high-pressure homogenizer (Microfluidizer® LM20, Microfluidics Inc., MA, U.S.A.). At the pre-treatment step, 0.5 wt% refined kenaf fiber in aqueous dispersion was disintegrated by a high-speed mixer (Xtreme Hi-Power Blender, MX1200XT, Waring, TX, U.S.A.) at 22,000 rpm for 10 min. After this pre-treatment step, the aqueous dispersion of refined kenaf fiber was passed through the homogenizer 10 times to obtain cellulose nanofibers (FCN). The process pressure was 207 MPa and the diameter of the chamber was 50 μm .

Preparation of CNF by TEMPO-mediated oxidation

Refined kenaf fiber was oxidized with the TEMPO/ NaBr / NaClO system in water [4]. 0.125 g of TEMPO and 0.8 g of NaBr were dissolved in 0.8 L of deionized water. Then, 8 g of refined kenaf fiber was added into the prepared solution, followed by addition of 20 mL of 2 M NaClO solution to remain at less than pH 10 with titration of 0.5 M NaOH solution for 10 h using an automatic titrator (COM-1700A, Hiranuma Sangyo Co., Japan). The oxidized fiber was washed and filtered by glass filter to remove excess reactants. 8 g of the TEMPO-oxidized cellulose was dispersed, and 9.1 g of NaClO_2 was dissolved in 800 mL of acetate buffer for oxidization of the remained aldehyde groups on cellulose to carboxyl groups. After washing with deionized water, the 0.4 wt% oxidized fiber dispersion was prepared and passed 2 times through the homogenizer at 207 MPa to obtain TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanofiber (TOCN).

Preparation of composite films

MMT powder was added to distilled water and the dispersion was stirred for 1 day to prepare 0.5 wt% of MMT dispersion. Aside from this, tetraethylammonium hydroxide solution was added to the MMT dispersion for the cation-exchange of the MMT interlayer to prepare modified MMT ($\text{MMT-N}^+\text{Et}_4$). The solution of tetraethylammonium hydroxide contained equimolar amounts of N^+Et_4 ion to Na^+ ion of MMT interlayer. CNF (FCN, TOCN) and MMT (MMT, $\text{MMT-N}^+\text{Et}_4$) were mixed all the combinations of their water dispersions for the preparation of CNF composites with 5 wt% MMT. The nanocomposite films were obtained by vacuum-filtrating on a membrane filter with a pore size of 0.1 μm , drying under vacuum pressure at 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ for over 12 h, and hot-pressing at 1 MPa, 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h.

2.3 Characterizations

FCN, TOCN, MMT and $\text{MMT-N}^+\text{Et}_4$ were deposited on mica, then their morphologies were observed using atomic force microscopy (AFM, NanoNavi II E-sweep, Hitachi High-Technologies Co., Japan).

The conversion ratios of carboxyl groups on the surface of CNF were evaluated by electric conductivity titration using an automatic titrator (COM-1700A, Hiranuma Sangyo Co., Japan). The cryogels of FCN and TOCN were dispersed in 7.1×10^{-4} wt% NaCl solution, respectively for the titration. The amount of the carboxyl group on the prepared FCN and TOCN was calculated from the amount of NaOH consumed for the coordination of Na^+ to carboxylate ions by following eq 1.

$$\text{Carboxyl group density (mmol/g)} = \frac{\text{NaOH (mL)} \times [\text{NaOH}] \text{ (M)} \times \text{NaOH factor}}{\text{Sample mass (g)}} \quad (1)$$

To measure the orientations of crystallites in the films, X-ray diffraction photographs were taken on imaging plates. The X-ray beam ($\text{CuK}\alpha$), generated using an X-ray diffractometer (RINT2000, Rigaku Co., Japan), was irradiated on the samples from the surface and edge directions. The X-ray diffraction profiles were also obtained using an X-ray diffractometer (RINT2100, Rigaku Co., Japan).

The mechanical properties of the prepared films were measured by tensile test using Autograph (AG-X Plus, Shimadzu Co., Japan). The specimens with 40 mm length and 5 mm width were measured at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. The measurements for more than six specimens were performed for each sample, and then the average values of Young's modulus, tensile strength and elongation at break were evaluated.

2.4 Stress transfer mechanism

Rectangular samples of the nanocomposites were set on the X-ray goniometer under stress. The stress σ_0 was applied to the whole specimen in the direction parallel to the sheet surface, as schematically shown in Fig. 1. The peak of 060 reflection of MMT observed at $2\theta = 62^\circ$ ($\text{CuK}\alpha$) was employed for the measurement of the change of lattice spacing. The lattice spacing d was calculated from the diffraction angle 2θ with the Bragg equation (eq 2),

$$2d \sin\theta = \lambda \quad (2)$$

where λ is the wavelength of X-ray beam (1.5418 Å for $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation). The crystal strain ε_c was estimated with the change of the lattice spacing before and after load as following equation (eq 3);

$$\varepsilon_c = \Delta d / d_0 \quad (3)$$

where d_0 shows the initial lattice spacing for the 060 reflection of MMT, and Δd is the change of the lattice spacing induced by the constant stress. Then, the stress σ_c on the incorporated MMT was calculated by following equation (eq 4);

$$\sigma_c = \varepsilon_c \cdot E_{in-plane} \quad (4)$$

where $E_{in-plane}$ is the in-plane elastic modulus (400 GPa [8]) for a single layer of MMT. More detailed descriptions were given in our previous papers [6, 9-10].

Figure 1: Schematic model of the measurement of the strain on the MMT nano-plates in nanocomposite by X-ray diffraction.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Structure

Fig. 2a and 2b show the AFM topological images of FCN and TOCN casted on mica. In the observation of FCN and TOCN, nanofibers were detected. The diameters of CNFs were calculated from the heights in their images as the number-averages of more than 50 points for each sample, FCN had approximately 18.8 ± 6.8 nm of the diameter, while TOCN had 2.7 ± 0.47 nm. The diameter of TOCN was

Figure 2: AFM topological images of a) FCN, b) TOCN, c) MMT and d) MMT-N⁺Et₄.

the similar size to that of single cellulose microfibril without bundling [11]. Thick fibers with 30 nm of the diameters were distributed only in FCN. These results indicated that homogeneous nanofiber was obtained only by TEMPO-oxidation treatment, not by mechanical fibrillation. Fig.2c and 2d show the AFM topological images of MMT and MMT-N⁺Et₄. Both MMT and MMT-N⁺Et₄ had the thickness with about 1.5 nm and the width with several hundred nanometers, which indicates that MMTs were successfully exfoliated to the nanolayers with 2D plate states.

Figure 3: Conductometric titration curves of FCN and TOCN.

In Fig. 3, the conductometric curves of FCN and TOCN were shown. It is revealed that the concentrations of carboxyl groups on FCN was 0.14 mmol/g-cellulose and on TOCN was 1.66 mmol/g-

cellulose. The value of TOCN suggested that, in the 6×6 cellulose fibril model, 97% of hydroxyl groups at 6-positions at the surface of the cellulose fibril were oxidized.

Figure 4: Wide angle X-ray diffraction profiles of FCN, TOCN, MMT, MMT- N^+Et_4 , FCN/MMT, TOCN/MMT, FCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 , and TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 .

Fig. 4 shows X-ray diffraction profiles of FCN and TOCN films, FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 , TOCN/MMT and TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 nanocomposites, and MMT, MMT- N^+Et_4 . In the diffraction profiles of the CNF films and nanocomposites, the 110/1-10 and 200 reflection peaks originated from cellulose I_β were observed at $2\theta = 16^\circ, 23^\circ$, respectively, which showed the crystal structures of cellulose were maintained even through mechanical and chemical fibrillation methods. The diffraction peaks of MMT and MMT- N^+Et_4 , at $2\theta = 6^\circ-8^\circ$ were observed, and assigned as 001 reflections of MMT. The peak of MMT- N^+Et_4 shifted to the side of lower angle, compared to MMT. The diffraction peak of the 001 reflection corresponded to the inter-layer distance in MMT. The shift of diffraction peaks means that the inter-layer cation was exchanged from Na^+ to N^+Et_4 . In the profiles of the nanocomposites, both the reflection of cellulose I_β and MMT were observed, which confirmed that composites were obtained successfully. Focusing on the 001 reflection of MMT, in the profiles of FCN/MMT and TOCN/MMT nanocomposites, their peaks were shifted to the side of lower angles and the peaks became broader. This implied that MMT in the nanocomposites could be partially exfoliated or intercalated by FCN and TOCN. On the other hand, in the profiles of FCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 and TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 nanocomposites, there was no difference from that of MMT- N^+Et_4 in the peak position and sharpness. These mean that that there was no room for FCN and TOCN to intercalate between the interlayers of MMT because of the stable interlayer of the MMT- N^+Et_4 , and nanofibers of FCN and TOCN would adsorb physically on the surface of MMT- N^+Et_4 .

Figure 5: X-ray diffraction photographs of FCN/MMT, FCN/ MMT- N^+Et_4 , TOCN/MMT, and TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 nanocomposites. The specimens were irradiated by X-ray beam in through direction (left) and edge direction (right) to the surface, respectively.

Fig. 5 shows the X-ray diffraction photographs of the FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 , TOCN/MMT and TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 nanocomposites. In the diffraction patterns with irradiation of X-ray beam from the through direction, the 110/1-10 and 200 reflections from cellulose I_β were observed as Debye-Scherrer rings. These indicate that the cellulose crystallites were distributed randomly in the in-plane diffraction. On the other hand, in patterns with irradiation of X-ray beam from the direction parallel to sheet surfaces, the 110/1-10 and 200 reflections from cellulose I_β , as well as 001 reflection of MMT appeared as arcs in the meridian direction. It was considered that the fiber axis of CNF and the layer of MMT were oriented in a direction parallel to the surface of the films.

3.2 Properties

Fig. 6 shows the stress-strain curves of FCN and TOCN films, FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄, TOCN/MMT and TOCN-MMT-N⁺Et₄ nanocomposites. In addition, the mechanical properties were provided from each stress-strain curve, as shown in Table 1. Compared with the FCN film, the FCN/MMT nanocomposite possessed higher Young's modulus, by the reinforcement effect by MMT, while FCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄ nanocomposites showed lower reinforcement effect. On the other hand, compared with the TOCN film, the TOCN/MMT nanocomposite showed higher Young's modulus, and also the TOCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄ nanocomposite showed much higher Young's modulus. These results would suggest the strong electrostatic interaction between the surfaces of TOCN and MMT-N⁺Et₄, which was attributed carboxylate anions on the fibril surface of TOCN and quaternary ammonium cations between layers of MMT-N⁺Et₄. This interaction led to different reinforcement effects of MMT in FCN and TOCN.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves of FCN, FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄, TOCN, TOCN/MMT, and TOCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄.

	Young's modulus	Tensile strength	Elongation at break
	GPa	MPa	%
FCN	9.5 ± 0.2	249 ± 9	5.8 ± 0.3
FCN/MMT	13.5 ± 0.9	301 ± 41	3.9 ± 1.0
FCN/MMT-N ⁺ Et ₄	11.1 ± 2.5	224 ± 76	3.1 ± 1.1
TOCN	12.2 ± 0.8	238 ± 24	4.9 ± 0.8
TOCN/MMT	14.8 ± 0.6	213 ± 47	1.7 ± 0.5
TOCN/MMT-N ⁺ Et ₄	16.5 ± 0.4	287 ± 27	2.4 ± 0.4

Table 1: Mechanical properties of FCN, FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄, TOCN, TOCN/MMT, and TOCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄.

To investigate the reinforcement in detail, we employed "X-ray diffraction method".

Fig. 7 shows the diffraction profile of TOCN/MMT nanocomposite before and under loading stress (σ_0). The peak of the 060 reflection of MMT shifted to lower angle side with increasing of σ_0 . This indicates that the lattice spacing of (060) plane of MMT was expanded by the tensile stress.

Fig. 8 shows the dependence of the stress on the MMT nanosheets σ_c on the stress applied to the whole specimen σ_0 measured by X-ray diffraction method under tensile stress. The plots were expressed

Figure 7: X-ray diffraction profiles of the MMT 060 reflection of the TOCN/MMT nanocomposite before and at loading.

Figure 8: Relationship between the stress σ_0 applied to the FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 , TOCN/MMT, TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 nanocomposites and the stress σ_c on the MMT crystallites.

with the straight line through the origin. The inclination σ_c/σ_0 of these lines was defined as the stress concentration factors. These factors indicate the efficiency of the stress transfer from the matrix to the incorporated MMT. The value of stress concentration coefficient for TOCN/MMT- N^+Et_4 was 16, which means that 16 times stress were concentrated on the MMT filler compared with the stress applied to the whole composite. It was assumed that the strong interfacial adhesion between TOCN and MMT- N^+Et_4 lead to the high efficiency of this stress transfer. Moreover, these coefficient had a positive correlation with the Young's modulus of these nanocomposites, suggesting that there is a relationship between the nano-scale states and the macro-scale mechanical properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We proposed cellulose nanofiber/montmorillonite nanocomposites by mixing their aqueous dispersions. In the nanocomposites, we used two types of cellulose nanofiber, made by high-pressure homogenizer (FCN) and TEMPO-oxidation methods (TOCN), and two types of montmorillonite with sodium (MMT) and quaternary ammonium cations (MMT- N^+Et_4) as interlayer ions. The TOCN/MMT-

N⁺Et₄ nanocomposite possessed high Young's modulus by the efficient reinforcement effect of MMT-N⁺Et₄ filler, but FCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄ nanocomposite show only slight reinforcement effect. Using X-ray diffraction method, it is revealed that the stress transferred to the incorporated MMT was 16 times higher than the stress applied to the whole nanocomposite for TOCN/MMT-N⁺Et₄. It was assumed that the strong interfacial interaction between TOCN and MMT-N⁺Et₄ leads to the higher efficiency of stress transfer, which results in higher mechanical performance of the nanocomposite.

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